

RESEARCH ON WAVE DEFECTS OF TAPE WINDING RESIN MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Curing process parameters and bandage method of vacuum auxiliary materials are studied in this paper to reduce waves. The results show that decreasing the rate of heating and increasing the temperature of pressured point can reduce waves by affecting the resin curing degree, and the bandage method without longitudinal fold can effectively avoid fiber tape deformation caused by vacuum auxiliary materials, thereby improving the surface quality of the product. The results of this article provide some reference for dealing with resin matrix composites which contain waviness and can be applied for further study.

1 Introduction

Resin matrix composites are widely used in all walks of life because of their excellent performances, but it is easy to form defects during the molding processes. Waves are common defects in the tape winding resin matrix composites, and adversely affect mechanical properties of the materials products. Most of the previous studies focused on the effect of wave defects on the properties of composite laminates, but there are few studies on preventing wave defects of composites, especially the tape winding resin matrix composites. Bogetti et al. [1] constructed a model for predicting the effect of waves on the stiffness and strength of composites based on classical laminate theory. Hsiao et al. [2] investigated the mechanical properties of composite laminates with three different types wave defects under composite load, and the results of experiments showed that waves led to a significant decrease in the compressive strength of the laminates. Wu et al. [3] adopted VARI process and the autoclave molding process to manufacture compression samples with different reinforced fibers and compression samples with fiber waviness defect, the results of the compression tests showed that Young's modulus and compressive strength degraded seriously with the increase of fiber waviness ratio, and fiber waviness had greater influence on compressive strength. Schmidt et al. [4] established failure theory research and analysis on the composite materials with folds. Fan [5] listed some general out-of-tolerance for laminated composite structures and introduced the reasons and the engineering treatment methods of fiber distortion. Zhuo et al. [6] estimated wrinkles within the composite laminates by their length/height ratio, and investigated the samples with wrinkles of different length/height ratio in the experiment. Guillaume et al. [7] analyzed the effect of waves on composite properties by simulation and finite element analysis. Zhu et al. [8] developed a multi-parameter analytic model based on the classical lamination theory to quantitatively investigate influence of out-of-plane waviness defect on the elastic properties (i.e. elastic modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratios) of composite laminates with waviness.

Waves refer to creases, wrinkles or bending deformations of one or more fiber layers formed inside or on the surface of composite products. There are four main reasons for the formation of waves in tape winding resin matrix composites: ① the shape of fiber tapes change from straight to sector during winding process. Especially the larger taper angle, the greater the deformation rate of the tape, and the more severe wave defects are formed; ② Under the action of temperature and tension, the fiber tapes slip and deform to form waves; ③ The vacuum auxiliary materials cannot be wrapped tightly around pre-formed product, and the vacuum bag shrinks after vacuuming to wave the fiber tapes during curing

process;④Under the action of pressure during curing process, the liquid resin is squeezed out and pre-formed product shrinks in the radial direction to form wave defects.

Among the above four reasons, the first one is determined by the deformation ability of fiber tape, and molding process parameters have little influence on it; the second defects type can be found in the winding process, and can be effectively improved by controlling the winding parameters; but the later two kinds of wave defects formed during curing process are irreversible, as shown in Fig.1. So controlling the wave defects during curing process is the main research content of this paper.

Figure 1: Wave defects of tape winding resin matrix composites: (a) composite sample; (b) composite sample without resin; (c) single fiber tape with wave defects.

2 Effect of curing process on wave defects

Curing process is important for resin. The viscosity of resin will decrease first and then increase with the increase of temperature during curing process, when the viscosity of resin is at a low level, the composite materials has good deformability. In order to achieve the compactness of product, a certain pressure is applied to the product during the curing process. When the viscosity of resin is low, resin is squeezed out easily and pre-formed product shrinks in the radial direction under the action of pressure, leading to the deformation of fiber tapes and the appearance of wave defects. Therefore, the matching of pressure and temperature during the curing process has a great influence on the occurrence of wave defects.

In order to prevent the occurrence of wave defects, the curing process parameters, the heating rate and the temperature of pressured point, were studied. Several resin samples were prepared at different heating rates (15, 20, 25 °C/h). One sample of the same heating rate was taken every other hour for infrared spectroscopy test to obtain the curve of hydroxymethyl index with temperature at different heating rates, as shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3.

Figure 2: Infrared spectroscopy curves of resin curing at different heating rates:

(a)15°C/h; (b)20°C/h; (c)25°C/h.

Figure 3: The curves of hydroxymethyl index with temperature at different heating rates.

The curing degree at each temperature was calculated according to the hydroxymethyl index (Fig.3), and the curve of curing degree and temperature with time was shown in Fig.4. It can be seen from Fig.4 that the sample with higher temperature has a higher curing degree at the same heating rate, while the sample with slower heating rate has a higher curing degree at the same temperature. For the resin, the higher curing degree, the lower resin viscosity, and the worse resin fluidity.

Figure 4: The curves of curing degree and temperature with time.

Tape winding resin matrix composite samples were prepared at different temperatures of pressured point and same heating rate (15 °C). The samples with pressure temperature above 100 °C had good appearance quality and almost no wave defects. But the density and tensile strength of product is lower than the normal level when the temperature of pressured point exceeds 102 °C, as shown in Table 1.

Sample Number	Temperatures of pressured point/°C	Density /kg/m ³	Tensile Strength/ MPa
1	95	1730	43.4~47.0
2	100	1680	42.1~43.4
3	102	1660	40.8~47.2
4	105	1620	33.4~37.5

Table1: Density and tensile strength of samples with different temperatures of pressured point.

Tape winding resin matrix composite samples were prepared at different heating rates (15, 20, 25°C/h) and the same temperature of pressured point(102°C), as shown in Fig.5. The surface of sample with a heating rate at 15°C/h had almost no wave defects, but the other samples had different degrees of wave defects. In order to verify the effect of heating rate on product performance, we tested the density and tensile strength of the composite, as shown in Table.2, and found that the decrease in heating rate caused a decrease in density. The tensile strength of samples with heating rate at 15~20°C/h are basically equivalent, but the tensile strength of sample with heating rate at 25°C/h which had worse wave defects were lower than other samples with slower heating rates, indicating that the wave defects have an influence on the mechanical properties of the product.

Figure 5: Tape winding resin matrix composite samples cured at different heating rates:

(a)15°C/h; (b)20°C/h; (c)25°C/h.

Sample Number	Heating rate /°C/h	Density /kg/m ³	Tensile Strength/ MPa
1	15	1660	40.8~47.2
2	20	1680	40.7~46.8
3	25	1710	35.9~37.4

Table2: Density and tensile strength of samples with different heating rates.

Through the above experiments, we can know that curing process have an effect on the wave defects of the tape winding resin composite, and we can reduce the wave defects by decreasing the heating rate or delaying the temperature of pressured point.

3 Effect of bandage method on wave defects

Autoclave curing is a common method for manufacturing composite material, and vacuum auxiliary materials are usually used during autoclave curing process. Vacuum bag is wrapped on the surface of the product and the product is densified under the action of vacuum and pressure.

Compared with the product size, the size of vacuum bag has a certain margin, which causes the vacuum materials to randomly wrinkle in any direction after vacuuming. During the curing process, as the temperature increases, the viscosity of resin decreases resulting in a certain fluidity of the resin and a certain deformability of the fiber tapes. The resin and fiber tape would fill any space in the vacuum bag, there is a possibility that the fiber tapes with resin are deformed and cured in the wave areas of the vacuum bag. So the wrinkle direction is important for the surface quality of the composites.

When the longitudinal space is formed after vacuum auxiliary materials were wrapped, the vacuum bag is contracted along the longitudinal direction to form longitudinal waves defects on the surface of composites after vacuuming. When the vacuum auxiliary materials were wrapped to form a spiral pleat, the vacuum bag is contracted along the spiral direction after vacuuming, and the spiral direction is parallel to the direction of the fiber tape layer, and no wave defects were formed. The contrast between the different bandage methods is shown in Fig.6.

Figure 6: Effect of bandage method on wave defects.

4 Conclusions

For resin matrix composites, we can obtain ways to reduce wave defects during the curing process through above analysis and experimentations. The results show that wave defects can affect the mechanical properties of the products, and curing process parameters and bandage method of vacuum auxiliary materials have serious impacts on wave defects. Decreasing the rate of heating or increasing the temperature of pressured point can reduce waves, but the ways can result in low product density. The vacuum bag with spiral direction fold or tightly wrapped on the surface of product can effectively avoid fiber tape deformation caused by vacuum auxiliary materials, thereby improving the surface quality of the product.

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